

The Role of Sino-Vietnamese Words in Reading Comprehension Texts of Literature Textbooks

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ABSTRACT: Sino-Vietnamese words play an extremely important role in the Vietnamese vocabulary system. Sino-Vietnamese words help the Vietnamese national language become refined and elegant. Besides, the expression in social communication is accurate, polite and cultural. The teaching of Sino-Vietnamese words in Vietnamese schools has achieved certain results, however, the teaching practice shows that the skills of recognizing and accurately using Sino-Vietnamese words are not simple for students. Therefore, we chose the research of the role of Sino-Vietnamese words in reading comprehension texts of Literature textbooks at the secondary school level, belonging to the book series *Connecting knowledge with life* to analyze the influence of Sino-Vietnamese words on the ability to identify, decode meaning and expand students' vocabulary in the reading comprehension process. The study aims to evaluate the level of support of Sino-Vietnamese words in improving students' linguistic thinking, reasoning ability and text perception.

KEYWORDS: Literature textbook, Reading comprehension text, Sino-Vietnamese words, Teaching and learning Sino-Vietnamese words.

1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Sino-Vietnamese words were created by the exchange and contact of Vietnamese and Chinese languages and cultures. They deeply reflect the development of thousands of years of history, culture, education, society as well as language, ideology and philosophical concepts of the nation. Over a long period of time, Sino-Vietnamese words have developed in both quality and quantity. They account for a large number, forming a rich and diverse vocabulary, contributing significantly to the formation, development and completion of the Vietnamese language system. However, the use of Sino-Vietnamese words in Vietnam still faces many difficulties and shortcomings. Even in the mass media or in daily life, there are many mistakes in the use of Sino-Vietnamese words due to confusion, errors and misunderstanding of the correct meaning of the words. Due to Vietnamese students' limited cognitive level, their knowledge of Vietnamese in general and Sino-Vietnamese words in particular is quite thin, making them confused and bewildered in approaching, learning and applying. That makes it difficult to develop, learn deeper, more difficult knowledge and solve exercises and other subjects. In addition, many teachers and students also face obstacles in getting acquainted with the 2018 general education program according to the capacity development orientation. Not only that, even students are confused and cannot adapt to new textbooks, teaching methods and new requirements of the current education program. The above makes teaching and learning Sino-Vietnamese words more difficult and requires a correct understanding of the role of Sino-Vietnamese words in reading comprehension texts in developing the Vietnamese language proficiency of high school students.

2. CONTENT

Sino-Vietnamese words are one of words of Chinese origin, with a phonetic shell of Sino-Vietnamese sounds, borrowed into the Vietnamese vocabulary after the 10th century and becoming a part of the Vietnamese vocabulary. If they are monosyllabic, they are often ancient and difficult to understand. If they are bisyllabic, they are structured according to Chinese syntax, with their own style (solemn, ancient, vague) different from the style of pure Vietnamese words (concrete, rustic, easy to understand).

The Literature textbooks, secondary school level (the book series *Connecting knowledge with life*) are compiled according to the 2018 General Education Program, aiming to develop students' language and literature skills. In particular, Sino-Vietnamese words play an important role in improving students' reading comprehension and language thinking skills. Our specific survey, in the Literature 7 textbook, includes 30 reading comprehension texts, most of which are modern texts, along with some folk and medieval literature texts. Through the survey, the frequency of Sino-Vietnamese words in reading comprehension texts is quite different,

depending on the genre, topic and purpose of conveying the content. Scientific and journalistic texts often have a higher density of Sino-Vietnamese words due to the requirement of precise and concise expression, while folk literature texts use more pure Vietnamese words to suit the cognitive ability of students.

The role and impact of Sino-Vietnamese words on the reading comprehension process of secondary school students are specifically studied as follows. First of all, we must mention the role of expanding vocabulary and improving the ability to express. In the field of linguistics and communication, expanding vocabulary and improving the ability to express are considered two key elements, having a dialectical relationship and interacting with each other. Sino-Vietnamese words in reading comprehension texts provide a huge amount of vocabulary for students in most areas of life. Helping students have a system of basic knowledge to enhance their ability to understand and use language, then they will have more opportunities to expand their knowledge.

Sino-Vietnamese words, an inseparable part of Vietnamese vocabulary, play an essential role in helping students deeply understand the culture and history of the nation. First of all, they reflect the system of traditional cultural values, from the ethical and moral systems to beliefs, religions and customs. Many Sino-Vietnamese words are associated with traditional cultural concepts and values, helping students understand more deeply the history and culture of the nation such as "saints", and "customs". Learning and understanding Sino-Vietnamese words deeply helps us gain more strength, have more "weapons" to conquer, explore and discover new values, especially cultural values and national history. Moreover, learning Sino-Vietnamese words also helps students better understand the cultural exchange relationship between Vietnam and China.

Sino-Vietnamese words help enhance students' reading comprehension. Sino-Vietnamese words, which form an important part of Vietnamese vocabulary, play a key role in enhancing students' reading comprehension, especially in the context of classical, formal or specialized texts. The general and abstract nature of Sino-Vietnamese words allows students to access and grasp complex concepts effectively. For example, the term "independence" not only denotes a state of freedom but also evokes a system of associations about national sovereignty and political autonomy.

Understanding and mastering Sino-Vietnamese words also helps students decode idioms, proverbs and allusions that frequently appear in most medieval texts. Sino-Vietnamese words can be considered an essential tool for students to approach and understand classic literary, historical and philosophical works. For example, understanding words such as "*beautiful woman*" (hong nhan), "*poor fate*" (bac menh), "*talent and fate are opposite to each other*" (tai menh tuong do) in *The Tale of Kieu (Truyen Kieu)* is a prerequisite for students to perceive the aesthetic and ideological value of the work. Thus, the process of learning Sino-Vietnamese words helps students expand their vocabulary, practice logical thinking and reasoning ability, thereby improving their ability to read and understand texts comprehensively and deeply. Many texts, especially medieval literary texts, use many Sino-Vietnamese words. Understanding the meaning of these words helps students grasp the content of the text more accurately, fully and deeply. In addition, Sino-Vietnamese words are often used to express formality and politeness in current informational texts, so grasping the meaning of words such as "keys" helps students decode the nuances of the text.

An extremely important role of Sino-Vietnamese words in students' reading comprehension is to form and develop accurate and profound abstract linguistic thinking, especially in the process of reading and understanding texts. The general and concise nature of Sino-Vietnamese words allows readers to approach and grasp complex concepts quickly and effectively. For example, when encountering the word "*change*" (vo thuong), readers not only understand it as change but also associate it with a profound philosophy about the nature of life. Mastering Sino-Vietnamese words not only helps readers improve their reading comprehension but also trains logical thinking, reasoning ability and expands vocabulary, thereby developing abstract linguistic thinking comprehensively. Learning Sino-Vietnamese words helps students practice the ability to analyze, synthesize, compare, and evaluate concepts more accurately and deeply.

It is undeniable that Sino-Vietnamese words have contributed to creating aesthetic values for texts, especially in traditional and modern literary works. Because Sino-Vietnamese words have a formal and concise style, they have brought a breath of fresh air to texts with an ancient and learned beauty, creating a difference from ordinary language. Not only that, the subtle combination of Sino-Vietnamese words and pure Vietnamese words creates sentences and verses rich in melody and rhythm, bringing high aesthetic effect. For example, in *The Tale of Kieu*, Nguyen Du skillfully used Sino-Vietnamese words such as "*hong quan*", "*tram anh*", "*san lai*", ... to create an artistic space that is both classical and familiar. The reasonable use of Sino-Vietnamese words not only helps the text become rich in images and emotions, but also has high evocative and suggestive power.

3. CONCLUSION

Sino-Vietnamese words play an important role in the Vietnamese vocabulary system, contributing to making the language more refined, elegant and helping social communication become more precise, polite and culturally rich. In general education, the teaching of Sino-Vietnamese words has achieved certain successes. Thereby, the study clarifies the impact of Sino-Vietnamese words on students' ability to recognize, decode meanings and expand their vocabulary, as well as evaluates the level of support of this type of word in developing linguistic thinking, reasoning ability and text perception. The results obtained will contribute to providing a practical basis for teaching and learning Sino-Vietnamese words in secondary schools, and at the same time suggest some further research directions to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning Sino-Vietnamese words in the Literature program.

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